

Healthy Sleep for Healthy Kids

A joint project by:

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A young girl is sleeping peacefully in a bed. She is wearing a white long-sleeved shirt. The bed is covered with a vibrant, multi-colored blanket featuring a cartoon character and floral patterns. The background is softly blurred, showing more of the room and another person in the distance.

**Sleep Hygiene
is choices we
make that will
help us to get
healthy sleep**

Why is sleep hygiene important to know?

Knowing what could help us sleep better and what could make it more difficult for us allows us to choose what to do and what to avoid in order to get the best and the right amount of sleep at the right time

**Habits that
make sure we
fall asleep
and wake up
at the right
time for us:**

**Go to bed
at the
same time
every
night**

Wake up at the same time every morning

**Exercise in the
early part of the
day**

**Relaxation or relaxing
activities before bedtime**

**Keep
cool**

- **Only get in bed when tired or sleepy**
- **Get out of bed if unable to sleep for 20 minutes**

Habits that make it difficult for us to get good sleep at the right time for us:

- **Going to bed and waking up at different times every night or almost every night**

A person is lying in bed in a dimly lit room. The person's head is resting on a pillow, and they appear to be looking towards the camera. The room has a wooden bed frame and a nightstand with a decorative leg. The overall atmosphere is quiet and somewhat somber.

• **Going to bed very late and waking up very late on the weekend confuses our body and makes it difficult to fall asleep**

**Taking long naps in the afternoon/
evening makes it difficult to fall asleep**

**Exercising near
bedtime will
also make it
difficult to fall
asleep**

Additional things that will make it difficult to fall asleep:

- **Having an argument or intense discussion before bed**
- **Using electronics in bed, watching tv right before bed**

Do not drink tea, cola, coffee, energy drinks in the evening

Tea, cola, coffee and energy drinks contain caffeine. Caffeine is a stimulant - it wakes you up and can make it more difficult to fall asleep if consumed close to bedtime

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Day
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**Sleeping
Children Around
the World**

www.scaw.org

Canadian Sleep
Society

Société Canadienne
du Sommeil

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